

A Study on Consumer Awareness And Usage of E-Banking Transactions through Mobile Phones in Thoothukudi

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Abstract

Internet Banking enables anytime access to the customer to give the customer's anytime access to their banks. Customers could check out their account details, get their bank statements, perform transactions like transferring money to other accounts and pay other bills sitting in the comfort of their homes and offices. However, the biggest limitation of Internet Banking is the requirement of the PC with an internet connection. Mobile Banking addresses the fundamental limitation of internet banking, as it reduces the customer requirement to just a mobile phone. Mobile usage has seen explosive growth in most of the Asian economics like India, China and Korea. The main reason that Mobile Banking scores over Internet Banking are that it enables, 'Anywhere, Anytime banking.' This paper highlights the awareness of customers towards the e-banking services provided by the banks.

Keywords: E-Banking, Mobile Banking and Internet Banking

Introduction

For the past two decades, the banking sector has chosen a new service channel based on the progress of information technology. The achievements and non- achievements of many retail banks is based on the abilities of managements to foresee and respond to changes in the financial market place. In the search for sustainable competitive advantage in the technological, financial services industry, banks have acknowledged the value of differentiating themselves from other financial institutions through distribution channels. This has lead to the development of banks and utilizing new alternative distribution channels to reach their customers. The customer is capable of carrying out banking transactions without his physical appearance at the bank which has made

security the ultimate requirement for the success of the transactions being carried out. It is an obligation for banks to apply a better strict security levels due to the many kinds of threats that have been recently identified with these alternative channels.

Review of Previous Studies

Mesther Krupa and Rajasekaran (2015) pointed out that E-banking is creating a lot of changes in the banking industry. Though all banking sector is providing e-banking, the main question is whether the customers are aware of all the e-banking services offered by their banks. So, it becomes necessary to study the customer awareness level towards e-banking services. 1

Bauer, H.H., Hammerschmidt, Falk, M.T (2007) said that to improve marketing resource allocation for corporate e-banking products and services e-banking services depends mainly on people's acceptance. The major finding is that although e-banking customers more or less have some common characteristics, they differ across different types of e-banking services.2

Tai-Kuei Yu and Kwoting Fang (2009) point out that with liberalization and internationalization in the financial market and progress in information technology, banks face dual competitive pressures to provide service quality and administrative efficiency. These recent developments that are fueled by technology might misleadingly suggest that the adoption of mobile banking is largely based on technological criteria.3

Statement of the Problem

The Indian banking sector is taking baby steps into this emerging area by offering non transactional banking on Mobile phone through SMEs like salary receipts, details of the last five transactions, stop payment request, etc., Nowadays because of advanced of technology, customer can make use of the banking services at a distance of one click from the mouse. Hence, there is a need to investigate the dimension of mobile banking services. This study is carried on to find out the customers awareness about mobile banking, their opinion regarding the problems faced and the reason for opting this technology in spite of other technologies. Therefore an attempt is made to analyze the mobile banking services in Thoothukudi.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are

- To know the different sources of information about mobile banking services.
- To find the reasons for using mobile banking services
- To find out the factors influencing the usage of mobile banking services

Methodology

The methodology is an essential aspect of any research. It enables the investigator to look at the research problem in a systematic, meaningful and orderly way. The methodology comprises of the sources of data collection, sampling design and techniques used for analyzing the data.

Sampling Design

A sample of 50 respondents was selected for the study. The researcher has adopted a simple random sampling technique for the collection of data from the respondents.

Field Work and Data Collection

The required information was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The researcher used the questionnaire for the collection of data from the respondents. A preliminary study was made

to pre-test the questionnaire with a few individuals and on that basis, the questionnaire was edited. The completed schedules were checked and corrected. The omissions and errors were rectified by revisits to the fields. The secondary data related to the present study have been collected from the books, journals, magazines and websites.

Processing of Data

After the completion of the data collection, the filled up questionnaire was edited properly. Codification was done for the responses collected. For further processing, a master table was prepared to sum up all the information collected. With the help of a master table, frequency tables were prepared for further analysis.

Frame Work of Analysis

Arithmetic mean and percentage analysis have been used to describe the data. The Chi-square test is used to test the association between Marital status and Limited Waiting time service and Bank account and Anytime, anywhere services. Ranking Index is found out by dividing the total scores by the frequency of responses.

Limitations of the Study

Every research suffers from errors and limitations. Some of these are inherent in the research design while some other becomes part of the study during various stages of operation. The present study is subject to the following constraints and limitations. The following are the limitations of the study: The convenience sampling method is followed in selecting the respondents. So the result of the study may be biased; As the study was conducted for a short duration, it was difficult to study in depth about the various aspects and Time, cost and other resources were constraints for a fully comprehensive study.

Results and Discussion

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no relationship between the Type of Bank and Anytime, Anywhere Services.

Table 1 Type of Bank and Anytime, Anywhere Services

Rows & Columns	O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
R1 C1	6	7.8	-1.8	3.24	0.415
R2 C1	5	6	-1	1	0.166
R1C2	13	12	1	1	0.083
R2C2	2	1.2	0.8	0.64	0.533
R1 C3	4	3	1	1	0.333
R2 C3	7	5.2	1.8	3.24	0.623
R1C4	5	4	1	1	0.25
R2C4	7	8	-1	1	0.125
R1 C5	0	0.8	-0.8	0.64	0.8
R2 C5	1	2	-1	1	0.5
	Total	50			$\chi^2=0.184$

Table 1 shows the relationship between the Type of Bank and Anytime, Anywhere Services. The table value of χ^2 for 4 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 9.49 and the calculated

value of χ^2 is 0.184. Since the calculated value is less than the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, it can be concluded that there is no significant relationship between the Type of Bank and Anytime, Anywhere Services.

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no relationship between the Marital Status and Waiting time.

Table 2 Marital Status and Waiting time

Rows & Columns	O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
R1 C1	6	7.8	-1.8	3.24	0.415
R2 C1	5	6	-1	1	0.166
R1C2	13	12	1	1	0.083
R2C2	2	1.2	0.8	0.64	0.533
R1 C3	4	3	1	1	0.333
R2 C3	7	5.2	1.8	3.24	0.623
R1C4	5	4	1	1	0.25
R2C4	7	8	-1	1	0.125
R1 C5	0	0.8	-0.8	0.64	0.8
R2 C5	1	2	-1	1	0.5
	Total	50			$\chi^2=0.184$

The above table shows the relationship between the marital status and the waiting time. The table value of χ^2 for 4 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 9.49 and the calculated value of χ^2 is 2.102. Since the calculated value is less than the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it can be concluded that there is no significant relationship between the marital status of the respondents and the waiting time.

Table 3 Factors Influencing the Use of Mobile Banking Services

Factors	Ranking by respondents					Total score	Mean score	Rank
	I	II	III	IV	V			
Fear about the security of transactions	5	7	6	12	20	115	2.3	V
Lack of technical knowledge	8	11	18	8	5	159	3.18	II
Lack of personal Advice	8	19	10	7	6	166	3.32	I
Not able to remember the PIN	11	10	11	11	7	157	3.14	III
Change in mobile	16	4	6	11	13	149	2.98	IV

The above table shows the ranking of the factors attracting the customers while using mobile banking services. It is inferred that the respondents are using mobile banking services mostly for 'Confidentiality.' So it is given the first rank. 'Saves time' and 'Round the clock access' got the second and third ranks respectively. The fourth and fifth ranks were given for 'Convenience' and 'Wide area network' and finally the sixth rank was given for 'Safety and security.'

Table 4 Problems in mobile banking service

Factors	Ranking by Respondents						Total score	Mean score	Rank
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI			
Wide area network	5	6	9	10	8	12	154	3.08	V
Saves time	22	4	7	11	2	4	221	4.42	II
Round the clock access	6	7	6	12	15	4	165	3.30	III
Confidentiality	13	18	9	3	6	1	226	4.52	I
Convenience	1	9	17	6	2	15	156	3.12	IV
Safety and Security	3	6	2	8	17	14	128	2.56	VI

Table 4 shows the problems in using mobile banking services. It is inferred that the respondents have a lack of personal advice. Hence, it is given the first rank. Lack of technical knowledge got the second rank, Not able to remember PIN got the third rank. Change in mobile got fourth rank and fear about the security of transactions got the fifth rank.

Table 5 Problems Faced

Problems	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Fear about Enquiry Facility	3	6
Lack of Technical Knowledge	24	48
Not able to remember the PIN	20	40
Change in mobile	3	6
Total	50	100

The above table shows the problems faced by respondents about mobile banking. 6% of the respondents have fear about the security of transactions, 48% on the lack of technical knowledge, 40% of the respondents faced PIN problems, 6% of the respondents faced problems due to change in mobile. Thus it is inferred that majority of the respondents have fear about the lack of technical knowledge.

Table 6 Reasons for Using Mobile Banking Services

Reason	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Provides anywhere bill payments	14	28
Money transfer facility	21	42
Monthly statements	2	4
Check account balances	8	16
Contact customerservices	5	10
Total	50	100

The above table shows the reason for using mobile banking services. 28% of the respondents use mobile banking services as it provides anywhere bill payments, 42% for money transfer facility, 4% for monthly statements, 16% for checking account balances and 10% to contact the customer services. Thus it is inferred that majority of the respondents use mobile banking services for transferring money.

Table 7 Source of Awareness

Source of Awareness	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Bank officials	15	30
Friends and Relatives	18	36
Advertisements	8	16
Agents	3	6
Displays in banks	5	10
Others	1	2
Total	50	100

Table 7 shows the source of awareness of respondents towards E-Banking. 30% of the respondents got awareness through bank officials, 36% through friends and relatives, 16% through advertisement, 6% through agents, 10% through Display in banks, and 2% through other sources. Thus it is inferred that majority of the respondents got awareness through friends and relatives.

Findings

It is found from the study that there is no significant relationship between the Type of Bank and Anytime, Anywhere Services, there is no significant relationship between the marital status of the respondents and the waiting time. Regarding the Factors Influencing the Use of Mobile Banking Services, Confidentiality is ranked first and saving of time was ranked second. From the evaluation of problems in using mobile banking services, lack of personal advice got the first rank and Lack of technical knowledge got the second rank. It was found that most of the respondents feared about the lack of technical knowledge, the majority of the respondents use mobile banking services for transferring money and the respondents mainly got awareness from friends, relatives and bank officials.

Suggestions

The following are the suggestions to improve electronic banking:

1. Software should be updated in such a way that the complaints like network failure can be minimized.
2. The facility of the stop payment, rectification of wrong payment, etc. may also be extended to online banking.
3. Awareness about mobile banking services must be created among the busy customers like promotional strategies.

Conclusion

Consumer awareness has the significant impact on interest to use in mobile banking. Consumers are interested because they have heard about it from somewhere & think that E-Banking will allow them to do banking transactions anytime. There is the significant impact of the usefulness of E-Banking on the interest to use E-Banking. Thus, if banks take more efforts in reaching out to consumers and give information about mobile banking, then more consumers will use mobile banking. Mobile banking will also reduce the cost of banks. There is the significant impact of ease of use of E-Banking on the interest to use E-Banking. Technology is now enabling consumers to do their banking transactions just by clicking some buttons on mobile or by sending SMS. So this is acting as a pull factor to increase adoption of electronic banking.

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